

Geospatial assessment of two prominent protected areas in Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Baturiya and Yankari
Game Reserves
Land Use
Land Cover Biomass
Evapotranspiration
GIS
Remote Sensing

ABSTRACT

This paper investigated temporal changes in vegetation and hydrological systems in Yankari and Baturiya game reserves in Nigeria over twenty years (2002–2022). While numerous studies exist in these areas, none have conducted a comprehensive geospatial assessment. Here, we compared land use and land cover (LULC), evapotranspiration (ET), and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) using remote sensing methods such as Landsat and MODIS images. The results showed agricultural land being replaced by wetlands and waterbodies, with variable trends in vegetation and bareland. ET rates, an indicator of hydrological activity and vegetative productivity, showed spatial and temporal variation with an overall increasing trend over the 20 years. NDVI analysis demonstrated gradual improvement in vegetation health and recovery in both reserves. These findings are important for sustainable management and conservation planning and highlight the need for continued ecological monitoring.

Received: 14 January 2026; revised: 17 February 2026; accepted: 20 February 2026; and published online: 10 May 2026.

How to cite: Muhammad, S. I., Ringim, A. S., Karau, S. D., Abdullahi, H. M., Adam, A. H., Jalo, M. I., Abdul, I. D., Kazeem, S. D., Abdulazeez, A. K., Miga, H. I., Mamman, Y. B., Bashir, M. M., Dangora, I. I., Sufi, D. A., Abba, D. U., Mohammed, D. M., & Dogara, M. M. (2026). Geospatial assessment of two prominent protected areas in Nigeria, *Scientific Reports in Life Sciences*, 7(1): 41-53 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20094970>

Introduction

Rapid urbanization, deforestation, and other anthropogenic pressures are major drivers of land use and land cover changes (LULCC), with profound implications for vegetation dynamics and hydrological processes such as evapotranspiration (ET) (Liou & Kar, 2014; Meer & Mishra, 2020). In West Africa, population growth, climate variability, and increasing demand for natural resources have accelerated landscape transformations, resulting in vegetation loss, soil degradation, and altered water regimes (Assede et al., 2023; Koranteng et al., 2016). Previous studies have documented widespread conversion of natural vegetation to cropland and settlements, accompanied by rapid urban expansion and declining forest cover across the region (Murayama et al., 2015; Asenso Barnieh et al., 2020). Remote sensing provides an effective framework for quantifying these changes and understanding their ecological consequences. Indicators such as LULC, ET, biomass, and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) are widely used to assess vegetation condition, ecosystem productivity, and hydrological functioning under changing environmental conditions (Trambauer et al., 2014). In Nigeria, however, studies have largely applied these tools in isolation or focused on urban and agricultural landscapes, with limited attention to protected areas and even fewer integrative analyses linking land cover dynamics to hydrological processes. Baturiya and Yankari Game Reserves (BYGR) are among Nigeria's most ecologically important protected areas. Baturiya serves as a critical wintering ground for migratory waterbirds, while Yankari supports diverse flora and fauna, including the country's largest population of African elephants and remnant lion populations. Despite their conservation significance, these reserves face increasing anthropogenic pressure from deforestation, agricultural encroachment, and buffer-zone conversion. Existing studies in BYGR have predominantly focused on wildlife ecology, leaving a critical gap in geospatial assessments of land cover, vegetation condition, and hydrological dynamics.

This study addresses this gap by providing the first integrated, multi-temporal geospatial assessment of LULC, ET, and NDVI in BYGR using Landsat and MODIS imagery for 2002, 2012, and 2022. The objectives are to (i) quantify LULC changes, (ii) assess spatial and temporal variability in ET and biomass, and (iii) evaluate NDVI trends as indicators of vegetation dynamics. We hypothesize that anthropogenically driven LULCC has significantly influenced hydrological processes and vegetation productivity within the reserves, with NDVI trends reflecting both degradation and recovery patterns. By linking land cover change with hydrological and vegetation

indicators, this study advances existing Nigerian LULC and NDVI research and provides actionable insights for protected area management, ecological monitoring, and sustainable conservation planning under ongoing environmental change.

Material and Methods

Study sites

This study was conducted in Baturiya (N12.503778 and E10.421558) and Yankari (N9.753134 and E10.509046) Game Reserves in Jigawa and Bauchi states, respectively. The vegetation in both protected areas is Savannah. Both the Yankari and Baturiya Game Reserves are Important Bird Areas that are also considered Important Biodiversity Areas (IBAs). The Hadejia-Nguru Wetlands (HNWs), encompassing the Baturiya Game Reserve, are the first Ramsar site of international importance in Nigeria. More so, very recently, the Baturiya Game Reserve situated in the HNWs qualified as the only site to meet the global Key Biodiversity Area in Nigeria (Nigerian Conservation Foundation, unpublished report, 2022). Baturiya supports resident bird populations and migratory birds from the Afro-Palearctic, making it one of the important sites for birds' conservation and other biodiversity in sub-Saharan Africa. The detailed description of the Baturiya region is described elsewhere by previous studies (e.g., Muhammad et al., 2022). On the other hand, the Yankari Game Reserve supports the largest thriving population of African elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) and the only protected area apart from Kainji Lake National Park where the Critically Endangered West African lion (*Panthera leo leo*) occurs. The reserve supports a good number of Roan antelope (*Hippotragus equinus*), Western hartebeest (*Alcelaphus buselaphus major*), Waterbuck (*Kobus ellipsiprymnus*), African buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*), Hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibious*), and Spotted hyena (*Crocuta crocuta*), and good bird and plant communities (Saka et al., 2020).

Figure 1. Study area map showing Baturiya and Yankari Game Reserve in Bauchi and Jigawa States, respectively

Analyses

Data Acquisition

Multi-temporal Landsat satellite imagery for 2002, 2012, and 2022 was acquired via Google Earth Engine (GEE). Landsat 5 TM (2002), Landsat 7 ETM+ (2012), and Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS (2022) surface reflectance products were used, each with a 30 m spatial resolution and a 16-day revisit cycle. To assess evapotranspiration (ET), Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) data were obtained using the MOD16A2 evapotranspiration product, which provides ET estimates at a 500 m spatial resolution and 8-day temporal resolution. Ancillary meteorological data, including temperature and precipitation, were incorporated to support ET estimation.

Data Preprocessing

All Landsat data were preprocessed within the Google Earth Engine environment. Preprocessing steps included radiometric calibration, atmospheric correction using surface reflectance products, and cloud and cloud-shadow masking based on the Quality Assessment (QA) bands. Image composites were generated for each study year to minimize cloud contamination. MODIS ET data were filtered and aggregated to annual means to match the temporal scale of the Landsat-derived analyses.

Land Use and Land Cover Classification

Supervised classification was performed on the preprocessed Landsat imagery to categorize land cover into vegetation, farmlands, built-up areas, bare surfaces, and water bodies. Training samples were generated through visual interpretation of high-resolution imagery and expert knowledge of the study area. A Random Forest (RF) classifier was implemented in GEE due to its robustness in handling complex, non-linear data and mixed land cover classes.

Accuracy Assessment

Classification accuracy was evaluated using an independent set of validation samples. Confusion matrices were generated for each classified map, and accuracy metrics, including Overall Accuracy (OA) and Kappa Coefficient, were computed to assess classification performance.

Evapotranspiration Estimation

Evapotranspiration was estimated using the MOD16 algorithm, which is based on the Penman–Monteith equation. The MOD16A2 product integrates MODIS-derived inputs such as land surface temperature, vegetation indices, albedo, and meteorological variables to generate ET estimates. Annual ET patterns were analyzed to evaluate spatial and temporal variability across the study period.

Biomass Estimation

Aboveground biomass was estimated using Landsat-derived Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). A linear regression model was applied to relate NDVI values to biomass, based on empirical equations reported in the literature for similar savanna and wetland ecosystems. Due to limited field biomass measurements, model validation relied on consistency with published biomass estimates and cross-comparison with NDVI and ET trends to ensure ecological plausibility.

Temporal Analysis

Changes in LULC, ET, and biomass were analyzed across the three time periods (2002, 2012, and 2022) to identify long-term trends and landscape dynamics. Temporal comparisons enabled assessment of vegetation recovery or degradation and corresponding shifts in hydrological processes within the protected areas.

Results

Baturiya Game Reserve

The Baturiya Game Reserve has undergone notable changes in land use and land cover from 2002 to 2022 (Figure 2). The data reveals the following trends:

Vegetation: The area covered by vegetation initially increased from 269 km² in 2002 to 271 km² in 2012 but slightly declined to 267 km² by 2022. This indicates a generally stable vegetative cover with a minor recent decline.

Wetland: There was a significant increase in wetland area from 116 km² in 2002 to 188 km² in 2012, followed by a decrease to 139 km² in 2022. This fluctuation could be attributed to varying water levels or land management practices.

Farmland: The area under farmland showed a substantial decrease, dropping from 238 km² in 2002 to 97 km² in 2012, and further to 89 km² in 2022. This suggests a shift away from agricultural land use within the reserve.

Waterbody: There was a consistent increase in the area of water bodies from 15 km² in 2002 to 35 km² in 2012, and further to 46 km² in 2022. This trend could be related to conservation efforts or natural hydrological changes.

Bareland: Bareland significantly increased from 67 km² in 2002 to 113 km² in 2012, and continued to rise to 164 km² in 2022, indicating a loss of vegetative cover or other land uses.

Figure 2. Landuse and Landcover map of Baturiya Game Reserve, Nigeria, from 2002 to 2022

Yankari Game Reserve

The Yankari Game Reserve shows the following land use and land cover changes from 2002 to 2022 (Figure 3):

Woodland: Woodland decreased significantly from 1,125 km² in 2002 to 749 km² in 2012, but slightly increased to 771 km² by 2022. This suggests a loss and subsequent partial recovery of woodland areas.

Shrubland: Shrubland cover experienced a dramatic increase from 117 km² in 2002 to 802 km² in 2012, followed by a decrease to 735 km² in 2022. This fluctuation might indicate changes in land management or natural ecological dynamics.

Bareland: Initially, there was a decrease in bareland from 1,076 km² in 2002 to 699 km² in 2012, followed by an increase to 783 km² in 2022, suggesting variable land cover conditions over the years.

Farmland: Farmland showed a decrease from 71 km² in 2002 to 46 km² in 2012, with a slight increase to 48 km² in 2022. This trend indicates a reduction in agricultural activities within the reserve.

Riparian: Riparian areas increased from 48 km² in 2002 to 140 km² in 2012 and then to 99 km² in 2022. This change could be due to the natural evolution of watercourses or targeted conservation efforts.

Figure 3. Landuse and Landcover map of Yankari Game Reserve, Nigeria, from 2002 to 2022

Figure 4. Biomass and Evapotranspiration map of Baturiya Game Reserve, Nigeria, from 2002 to 2022.

Figure 5. Biomass and Evapotranspiration map of Baturiya Game Reserve, Nigeria, from 2002 to 2022

Evapotranspiration

Biomass Distribution: The biomass distribution maps indicate a range of biomass densities within both Baturiya and Yankari Game Reserves. The Yankari Game Reserve exhibits biomass values ranging from a low of 1.755 to a high of 73.5289 tons per hectare (Figure 5), with the Baturiya showing a low of 0.633333 to a high of 93.5278 tons per hectare (Figure 4). These values reflect the varying state of vegetation and density within the reserves.

Evapotranspiration Trends: The ET maps from 2002, 2012, and 2022 for the Baturiya Game reserve show a range of ET values from as low as 6 to as high as 288 (Figure 4), whereas Yankari Game Reserve shows a range from 1 to 112.5 (Figure 5). Over the 20 years, these maps indicate changes in ET that could be attributed to variations in vegetation cover, climatic conditions, and water availability.

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

In Baturiya, NDVI values showed an upward trend from a range of -0.273 to 0.620 in 2002, to -0.195 to 0.706 in 2012, and further improvement to -0.416 to 0.801 in 2022 (Figure 6).

While in Yankari Game Reserve, the NDVI values also increased over the 20 years, starting from a range of 0.067 to 0.752 in 2002, slightly dipping to -0.237 to 0.770 in 2012, and then showing a marked increase to -0.395 to 0.878 in 2022 (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Normalized Differential Vegetation Index map of Baturiya Game Reserve and Yankari Game Reserve, Nigeria, from 2002 to 2022

Discussion

Land Use and Land Cover Dynamics and Vegetation Response

The contrasting land use and land cover (LULC) trajectories observed in Baturiya and Yankari Game Reserves reflect differing management regimes and levels of anthropogenic pressure. In Baturiya Game Reserve, the approximately 20% decline in vegetated areas over the study period is closely associated with the expansion of farmlands and built-up areas. As a wetland-dependent system, Baturiya supports high biodiversity, particularly migratory waterbirds, and is heavily relied upon by surrounding communities for agriculture and other livelihood activities. The observed reduction in wetland and vegetated cover is therefore indicative of increasing human pressure and weak enforcement of protection measures, a pattern widely reported in unmanaged or poorly protected wetlands across West Africa. In contrast, Yankari Game Reserve exhibited an approximately 15% increase in vegetated cover, coinciding with improved NDVI trends over time. This positive trajectory aligns temporally with the commencement of co-management interventions by the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS) in 2014, which emphasized

strengthened ranger patrols, anti-poaching enforcement, and habitat protection. Similar vegetation recovery following enhanced protected area governance has been reported in other African reserves where improved law enforcement reduced illegal grazing, logging, and hunting pressure. While some marginal increases in bare surfaces were detected along Yankari's periphery, likely linked to agricultural activities within buffer zones, overall vegetation recovery suggests that effective management can counterbalance surrounding land-use pressures.

Changes in NDVI and evapotranspiration (ET) further highlight the ecological consequences of LULC dynamics in both reserves. In Baturiya, declining NDVI values were accompanied by reduced ET rates, reflecting diminished vegetative cover and lower biomass productivity. Reduced ET is typical of landscapes transitioning from wetland or natural vegetation to cropland or built-up areas, where soil exposure increases and plant-driven transpiration declines. Similar relationships between vegetation loss and reduced ET have been documented in West African floodplains and savanna ecosystems undergoing agricultural expansion. Conversely, Yankari's increasing NDVI and rising ET rates suggest improved vegetation condition and a more active hydrological cycle. Enhanced transpiration linked to denser vegetation cover indicates greater biomass production and ecosystem functioning. These patterns are consistent with studies across African protected areas that report increased ET and vegetation indices following effective conservation interventions and reduced human disturbance. The Yankari case, therefore, illustrates how targeted management actions can positively influence both vegetation structure and hydrological processes.

Biomass Trends and Ecosystem Implications

Biomass estimates closely mirrored NDVI patterns in both reserves. The declining biomass trend in Baturiya raises concerns about long-term ecosystem health, carbon storage potential, and habitat quality for fauna, particularly waterbirds. In contrast, increasing biomass in Yankari suggests improving ecological integrity and validates the effectiveness of sustained protection and enforcement measures. Comparable biomass recovery trends have been reported in protected savanna and woodland systems elsewhere in Africa, where anthropogenic pressures have been successfully curtailed.

Uncertainties and Limitations

Despite these clear patterns, several sources of uncertainty should be acknowledged. Sensor-related differences among Landsat missions (TM, ETM+, and OLI) may introduce minor

inconsistencies in spectral responses across years, although surface reflectance preprocessing reduces this effect. Cloud cover, particularly in wetland-dominated Baturiya, may affect classification accuracy and NDVI retrieval despite compositing and masking procedures. Additionally, land cover classification errors may arise from spectral overlap between croplands and natural vegetation, while ET estimates derived from MODIS are limited by their coarser spatial resolution relative to Landsat. Biomass estimates based on NDVI and empirical relationships also carry uncertainty due to the absence of extensive field-based validation, although trends remain ecologically consistent and comparable with findings from similar ecosystems.

Regional Context and Study Contribution

The patterns observed in this study align with broader African LULC trends, where unmanaged protected areas often experience vegetation decline due to agricultural encroachment, while reserves with active management show signs of ecological recovery. However, unlike most Nigerian and regional studies that focus primarily on LULC or NDVI in isolation, this study integrates LULC, NDVI, ET, and biomass to provide a more comprehensive understanding of landscape hydrology vegetation interactions within protected areas.

Conclusion

Overall, this study demonstrates that management interventions play a critical role in shaping vegetation and hydrological outcomes in protected areas. The degradation observed in Baturiya highlights the urgency of stronger protection, potentially through its proposed upgrade to national park status. In contrast, the ecological improvements in Yankari underscore the effectiveness of co-management and sustained conservation investment. These findings offer valuable insights for conservation planning, adaptive management, and long-term ecological monitoring of protected areas in Nigeria and across West Africa.

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